

Changing Scenario of Agriculture in Madhya Pradesh: Prospects & Challenges. 171/13.

Effect of *Andrographis paniculata* on *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus* species

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There is an overprovision of chemicals for the control of plant diseases. But owing to rising consciousness, these chemicals, on account of their ill-effects, are being put on hold. Rather, emphasis is being laid on bio-controlling agents and making use of eco-friendly & safe alternative methods.

Andrographis paniculata has been used in traditional *Siddha* and *Ayurvedic* systems of medicine in India since medieval times. It has been popular even in tribes of India and elsewhere for multiple clinical applications. During present investigation, chemical characterization and efficacy of *Andrographis paniculata* were observed, *in vitro*, on seed borne fungi *Aspergillus* and *Rhizopus*. The growth of the fungal species was inhibited significantly ($p < 0.02$) with both alcoholic as well as water extract of all ages and of the concentrations used. The alcoholic leaf extracts of *Andrographis paniculata* were more effective in comparison to aqueous extract as long as the growth retardation of *Rhizopus* and *Aspergillus* was concerned. However, in separate experiments, the crude aqueous and alcoholic leaf extracts of *Andrographis paniculata* were found to be inhibitorier for *Aspergillus* as compared to *Rhizopus* in the artificial culture media. Leaf extracts of *Andrographis paniculata* are easy on pocket, environmentally safe, assure fine crop yield and are unswerving to guard the crops against fungal infestations.

Keywords: *Andrographis paniculata*, *Aspergillus*, Fungicide, *Rhizopus*.

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